

Synthesis of Furano Compounds. Part XX. Synthesis of Some Dibenzofurans from Cyclohexan-1,3-diones

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The facile synthesis of 1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran from dihydroresorcinol and chlorocyclohexanone has been extended and several substituted dibenzofurans have been prepared by this route.

Degradation work on rhodomartyxin is reported to give a dimethyldibenzofuran containing both the methyl groups in the same ring¹ and degradation of some lichen products containing dibenzofuran nucleus is known to give simple substituted derivatives of dibenzofuran. For the direct synthesis of substituted dibenzofurans, usually the general method of Ebel² is employed. In this synthesis, 2-bromocyclohexanone is condensed with a sodium phenoxide and the resulting keto-ether is cyclised and dehydrogenated³ and a counterpart of this reaction, developed in this laboratory, lies in the condensation of 2-chlorocyclohexanone with cyclohexan-1,3-dione to 1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran⁴. The experiments described in this communication were undertaken to study the scope and limitations of this simple synthesis. The result has led to the preparation of some dibenzofurans, substituted at different positions.

The condensation of 1-methylcyclohexan-3,5-dione (I) with 2-chlorocyclohexanone proceeded smoothly-giving 1-keto-3-methyloctahydrodibenzofuran (II). This compound, which showed a carbonyl absorption at 6.19μ , was next reduced to the crystalline alcohol (III) by lithium aluminium hydride and then smoothly dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal to 3-methyldibenzofuran. By the action of methylmagnesium iodide on (II), hexahydro-1,3-dimethyldibenzofuran (V) was isolated and this on dehydrogenation afforded 1,3-dimethyldibenzofuran.

1-Methylcyclohexan-2,4-dione⁵ (VII) has now been conveniently prepared by the catalytic reduction of 1-methyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzene with Raney nickel in alkaline solution⁶. This on similar condensation with 2-chlorocyclohexanone gave a mixture of the two possible 2- and 4-methyl derivatives (VIII) and (IX) respectively. As their separation proved difficult, the mixture was reduced, dehydrogenated, and then oxidised by potassium permanganate to a mixture of dibenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid and dibenzofuran-4-carboxylic acid, which were separable by fractional crystallisation.

1. Trippett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 414.

2. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929, 12, 3.

3. Cf. Trippett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 418.

4. Chatterjea and Ray, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 998.

5. Gilling, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 2029.

6. Cf. King and Felton, *ibid.*, 1948, 1371.

It appeared desirable to prepare derivatives of 2-methyldibenzofuran from the readily accessible 1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran. For this purpose, the latter was converted into the hydroxymethylene derivative (X) in an attempt to effect the well-known Sen-Mandal methylation⁷. As the methylation unaccountably failed, the hydroxymethylene derivative was benzoylated in pyridine solution to (XI) and then catalytically reduced with the aid of Adams' catalyst in acetic acid till two moles of hydrogen were absorbed when the formation of (IX) resulted⁸. This was converted as before into pure 2-methyldibenzofuran. The hydroxymethylene derivative (X) on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave a mixture of the iso-oxazoles (XII) and (XIII)⁹ and the latter on methylation in butanol¹ in presence of potassium butoxide¹ afforded the nitrile (XIV)¹⁰.

Hydrolysis of the keto-nitrile in acid solution was slow and we were able to isolate the amide only under vigorous conditions.

7. This *Journal*, 1928, 5, 606; Cornforth and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1865.

8. Cf. Astill and Bockelheide, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4079.

9. Cf. Johnson and Shelberg, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 1745.

10. Cf. Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1947, 69, 2942.

It is clear that an unequivocal synthesis of 4-methyl derivatives of dibenzofuran may be effected by condensation of dihydroresorcinol with 2-bromo-6-methylcyclohexanone. The latter is difficultly accessible by bromination of 3-methyl-2-oxocyclohexanecarboxylic acid followed by decarboxylation¹¹; the details of its preparation have not yet been published. The direct bromination of 2-methylcyclohexanone affords the 2-bromo derivative¹¹. In the event, an attempt was made to condense 6-bromo-2-dimethylaminoethylcyclohexanone (XV)¹² with dihydroresorcinol, but without success. Model experiments were carried out to effect bromination of 2-methylcyclohexanone at the unsubstituted site by way of the hydroxymethylene compound. Thus the bromo-aldehyde (XVI), obtained by bromination of the copper or sodium salt of hydroxymethylene acetophenone¹³, has now been found to undergo hydrolysis with the extrusion of the formyl group, yielding phenacyl bromide.

Similar results have been obtained with several substituted acetophenones, but in the cyclohexanone series, pure products could not be obtained. It may be mentioned that fluorination of the sodium salt of 2-oxymethylenecyclohexanone with perchloryl fluoride in ethanol has been reported to furnish 2-fluorocyclohexanone¹⁴.

11. Rinne *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5759; Nazarov *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 1082.

12. Land *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 125.

13. Garg *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 353; 1957, **34**, 286.

14. Kende, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 14, p. 13.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Condensation of 1-Methylcyclohexan-3,5-dione with 2-Chlorocyclohexanone.—To a solution of 1-methylcyclohexan-3,5-dione¹⁵ (1.3 g) in aqueous potassium hydroxide (0.56 g. in 3 ml water) was added a solution of 2-chlorocyclohexanone (1.4 g.) in methanol (10 ml) and the mixture stirred vigorously at the room temperature. After 2 hours the mixture became turbid and colorless plates of 1-keto-3-methyloctahydrodibenzofuran (II) began to appear. After stirring for 1 hour more, the product was collected, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol as colorless shining plates (1.3 g.), m.p. 102°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 8.0. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 76.4; H, 7.9%). λ_{max}^{alc} 280 m μ (log ϵ , 3.5) (1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran also absorbed maximally at 280 m μ ; log ϵ , 3.5). The compound showed a carbonyl absorption at 6.19 μ (KBr disc). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red plates, m. p. 267°. (Found: N, 15.0. $C_{10}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 14.5%).

3-Methylidibenzofuran.—The above ketone (0.4 g.) on reduction with $LiAlH_4$ (0.2 g.) in ethereal solution gave 3-methyl-1-hydroxyoctahydrodibenzofuran (0.3 g.) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colorless needles, m.p. 106°. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 8.6. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 75.7; H, 8.8%). On dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (0.1 g., 10%) at 300° for 3 hours, the above carbinol (0.25 g.) afforded 3-methylidibenzofuran which was isolated by distillation under reduced pressure. The compound crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 66° (Suggi and Shindi¹⁶ recorded m.p. 61–62°; Kruber and Marx¹⁷ recorded m.p. 66°). (Found: C, 85.7; H, 5.5. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}O$: C, 85.7; H, 5.5%).

1,3-Dimethylidibenzofuran.—A solution of the foregoing ketone (1.0 g.) in ether (50 ml) was added to an excess of methylmagnesium iodide from methyl iodide (2.2 g.) and magnesium (0.3 g.) in ether (30 ml). After refluxing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the product was worked up to afford 1,3-dimethyl 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydrodibenzofuran (V) (1.0 g.) which crystallised from benzene-ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 82.8; H, 8.0. $C_{14}H_{18}O$ requires C, 83.1; H, 8.9%). On dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal for 6 hours, 1,3-dimethylidibenzofuran was obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 212–15°/40mm (Trippett¹ records m.p. 45°). (Found: C, 85.2; H, 6.3. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O$: C, 85.7; H, 6.1%). The *picrate*, prepared in ethanol, melted at 85°.

1-Methylcyclohexan-2,4-dione^{6,18}.—A solution of 4-methylresorcinol (7.0 g.) in aqueous NaOH (2.4 g. in 15 ml water) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of Raney nickel (2 ml sediment) when slow absorption of hydrogen took place. The absorption of hydrogen (1 mole) was complete in 8 hours. The mixture was filtered, the filtrate made acid to Congo red, and then extracted with chloroform. On removal of the solvent, 1-methylcyclohexan-2,4-dione (4.9 g.) was obtained as a viscous, syrupy mass which later slowly solidified, m.p. 65–70°. On condensation with formaldehyde, the bis-derivative was obtained as fluffy needles from ethanol, m.p. 136°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 7.3. $C_{13}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 68.1; H, 7.6%).

Condensation of 1-Methylcyclohexan-2,4-dione with 2-Chlorocyclohexanone.—The above dione was condensed with 2-chlorocyclohexanone as before and the product consisting

*All m.p.'s are uncorrected.

15. Crossley and Renauf, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 105, 602.

16. *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1934, 54, 410.

17. *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 2478.

18. *Organic Synthesis*, Coll. Vol. III, p. 278.

of a mixture of 2-methyl- and 4-methyl-octahydro-1-ketodibenzofurans separated as a brown viscous liquid, b.p. 144-50°/3 mm, giving an orange-red dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 255° with sintering; yield was about 50%. The mixture (5.0 g.) was reduced with LiAlH_4 as before to give a mixture of the carbinols in the form of a brown oil, which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (0.5 g., 10%) gave a mixture of 2- and 4-methyldibenzofurans distilling at 200°/40mm. The mixture had no tendency to solidify even on admixture with authentic 2-methyldibenzofuran (m.p. 45°).

On oxidation with an excess of 2% KMnO_4 solution for 8 hours, the mixture gave a product, m.p. 175-244°. On fractional crystallisation from ethanol this gave dibenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid, m.p. 246-48°. (First crop Mayer and Krieger¹⁹ give m. p. 246-47°). (Found: C, 73.1; H, 3.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$: C, 73.6; H, 3.9%). The second crop, m.p. 236-40°, was impure 2-carboxylic acid and the third crop, m.p. 175-90°, consisted mainly of dibenzofuran-4-carboxylic acid. This on further purification melted at 205-209°, undepressed on admixture with dibenzofuran-4-carboxylic acid, m.p. 209-10° (Kruber²⁰).

2-Formyl-1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran.—A solution of ethyl formate (1.5 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml) was added to cooled, powdered sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.46 g.). To the cooled, stirred mixture a solution of 1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran (1.9 g.) in benzene (13 ml) was added. The entire mass turned pink and the product was left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day the mixture was treated with iced water and the aqueous layer separated. The benzene solution was extracted twice with dilute NaOH solution and the combined aqueous solution was acidified with HCl (dil.). The *hydroxymethylene compound* (1.3 g.) crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow needles, m.p. 103-104°. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 6.7. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.5; H, 6.5%). The compound gave a bluish green ferric reaction.

Attempted Methylation.—A mixture of the above hydroxymethylene compound (0.6 g.), methyl iodide (1.2 ml), and methanolic sodium methoxide (sodium, 0.05 g. in 2 ml methanol) was heated in a small pressure bottle at 100° for 20 hours. The resulting product was refluxed with *N*-HCl (8 ml) for 5 minutes and then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute alkali, dried, and the solvent removed to give a brown viscous gum (ca. 0.1 g.). As the product did not give a red 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, the expected compound (IX) was not formed.

2-Benzoyloxymethylene-1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran (XI).—The foregoing hydroxymethylene compound (1.6 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (5 ml), cooled, and treated slowly with benzoyl chloride (1.2 g.). The mixture was left overnight at the room temperature and then treated with HCl (dil.). The resulting *benzoyl derivative* (0.4-0.6 g.) was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid as slender needles, m.p. 196-97°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 5.5%).

Catalytic Reduction.—A solution of the above benzoyl derivative (0.2 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of Adams' catalyst (0.05 g.). The uptake of hydrogen was very quick and the reduction was interrupted when 2 moles of the gas were absorbed. The catalyst was removed by filtration and the resulting clear solution, which turned pink on exposure to atmosphere, was concentrated to 2 ml

19. *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1861.

20. *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1382.

and then taken up in ether and washed with alkali to remove acetic and benzoic acids. On removal of ether an oil was obtained (giving a red 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 235°, uncrystallised) which was reduced with LiAlH_4 as before and dehydrogenated at 300°C for 3 hours with palladised charcoal (10 mg., 10%). 3-Methyl-dibenzofuran was isolated by distillation as a solid (0.02 g.), m.p. 43-45°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (m.p. 45°) obtained by the Wolff-Kishner reduction of 2-formyl-dibenzofuran.

1-Keto-2-methyl-2-cyano-octahydrodibenzofuran. — 2-Hydroxymethylene-1-keto-octahydrodibenzofuran (1.6 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (40 ml) and treated with finely powdered hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g.). The mixture was refluxed in an oil bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, then diluted with hot water till turbidity appeared, and left overnight in a refrigerator. The separated solid was first crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether and then recrystallised from acetic acid, affording the *iso-oxazole* (XII) (0.1 g.) as bright colorless plates, m.p. 176-77°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 6.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0%). The filtrate on concentration gave a solid which on recrystallisation afforded the isomeric *iso-oxazole* (XIII) (0.5 g.) as colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 105-106°. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 5.9. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0%). This *iso-oxazole* (0.4 g.) was added to a solution of potassium (0.25 g.) in dry butanol¹ (10 ml) and the mixture heated in an oil bath (75-80°) for 15 minutes. Afterwards the mixture was refluxed (bath temperature 90-100°) and methyl iodide (2 ml) was added dropwise during 10 to 15 minutes. After refluxing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the solvent was removed by distillation; the residue was treated with water and extracted with benzene. The *keto-nitrile* (XIV) (0.05 g.) crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 104-105°. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 6.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 73.5; H, 6.6%).

Hydrolysis.—A mixture of the above nitrile (0.04 g.), acetic acid (1.5 ml), and hydrobromic acid (0.5 ml, 48%) was refluxed vigorously for 3 hours. On working up, the amide was obtained, crystallising from dilute ethanol in colorless plates (0.02 g.), m.p. 137-38°. (Found: N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 5.7%).

Deformylation of α -Bromo- α -formylacetophenones.— α -Bromo- α -formylacetophenone, its *p*-methyl-, *p*-bromo-, and *p*-chloro derivatives were prepared according to Garg *et al.*¹³ by bromination of copper complex of the related hydroxymethylene compounds. The last named compound, viz. *p*-chloro- α -bromo- α -formylacetophenone, was obtained as a colorless solid, m.p. 120-21°. Garg *et al.*¹³ give m.p. 108°; Mukherjee²¹ records m.p. 102-103°. (Found: C, 40.8; H, 2.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{BrCl}$: C, 40.4; H, 2.3%).

For deformylation, the compounds were refluxed with normal hydrochloric acid for 1 hour and then isolating the deformylated compound by steam distillation. In this way, phenacyl bromide, m.p. 56-58°, *p*-methylphenacyl bromide, m.p. 46-48° (from ethanol), *p*-bromophenacyl bromide, m.p. 118° (from ethanol), and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide, m.p. 103° (from ethanol) were isolated in about 40-60% yield.

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